

Matching Function and Technology: Communication for Safety Applications and Superior User Experience

Andre Hainzmaier, Dr. Johannes Reschke, Dr. Werner Thomas

AUDI AG, Germany

Keywords: OLED, Hazard Warnings, Interaction, Autonomous Vehicles

1 Abstract

Conducting a study on the optimal position of upcoming communication features for safety applications, we found that regarding hazard warnings, participants focused on the vehicle's rear, while taillights (max. 75%) and rear window (max. 63%) were the most important positions. The closer participants get to preceding vehicles, the more important are taillights for communication of warning signals.

2 Introduction

In the context of “Exterior User Experience” at AUDI, we start our thinking from the perspective of the customer and match the right function with the perfect technology.

Using front and rear lamps for communication is an increasingly big topic within the Automotive Lighting community and research was already conducted especially about warnings in rear-combination lamps (RCL) [1]. In general, it was stated that the ongoing use of informal signs in road traffic is an indispensable aid for structuring traffic flow [2].

At AUDI we already started to introduce communication functions, like “proximity indication”, into RCLs since 2020. The selected technology in RCLs is OLED-based, as it enables both communication and styling in a single component.

By combining function and technology in an intelligent way, we seek to generate a superior User Experience for our customers. Therefore, we conducted the survey to identify the optimal position for external communication in safety applications.

3 Survey on the optimal position for communication

We conducted a guided online-survey with 38 participants. Other than common approaches, we did not use eye tracking and rough estimations for region of interests, but rather a detailed and exact marking tool [3].

METHOD

We conducted the survey using the software “Microsoft” Skype and its shared drawings function showing three different views the AUDI A6 Avant e-tron concept (see Figure 1). The investigator explained to the subjects that they should mark at least one area in the front, side or rear of the vehicle where they would expect an external communication to be displayed. They should also include the exact size of the communication signs in their marking ignoring any technological constraints as shown in the examples given to them (see Figure 1). To interpret the different markings, we also asked the test persons to explain why they had chosen the specific area they marked. Afterwards screenshots of each subject’s markings were made and saved with a randomized participant-ID.

Figure 1: Example provided to the participants how to mark certain positions

We used six different traffic situations where an external communication might be needed for others to understand the situation and get safety relevant information (see Figure 2). Situation a) was an exit warning (door opening) scenario, e.g. to warn bicyclists. Situation b) to d) were three similar scenarios with several possible hazards (emergency braking, objects on road, traffic jam, etc.) that might occur at different distances. The distances were 50-100 m (Figure 2b), 30-70 m (Figure 2c) and below 30 m (Figure 2d). Situation e) showed a distance warning scenario with a tailgating vehicle at distances below 30 m. Finally, situation f) was an autonomous parking

scenario on a parking lot where the vehicle should inform others about its active autonomous parking mode.

Figure 2: Different situations used for the survey, a) exit warning, b) hazardous situations 50-100 m distance, c) hazardous situations 30-70 m distance, d) hazardous situations <30 m distance, e) distance violation, f) autonomous parking [4, 5]

For each situation and group, we combined the markings to colormap images in MATLAB to identify common preferences in positioning of external communication (e.g. Figure 4). Hence, heatmaps of all answers were aggregated for each scenario.

SAMPLE DESCRIPTION

In our sample of the described survey, we had 38 participants, including four women and 34 men, while all 19 participants of group 2 had no background on exterior lighting (see Figure 3). Ages can be divided in five groups, 18-27 years (31 %), 28-35 years (21 %), 36-43 years (18 %), 44-52 years (21 %), and 53-67 years (9 %).

In group 1, consisting of light department members, 50 % had some and 21 % a lot of experience with external communication. In group 2, with participants from different AUDI departments, nobody had any prior knowledge of external communication. We asked the participants to use a desktop PC (24 %) or Notebook (76 %) and thus, 82 % used a mouse for marking regions of interest while only 18 % used their touchpad or digital pencils.

Figure 3: Knowledge on communication for group 1 (light department) and group 2 (other departments)

RESULTS

For each situation the heatmaps were created for all 38 subjects combined and separately for the 19 light department members and the 19 participants from other departments. Over all situations, the participants focused for external communication mostly on taillights (max. 47 %) and rear windows (max. 42 %) as shown in Figure 4. Some participants also used projections around the vehicle, lamps on opening doors and daytime running lights. For the combined markings in situation a)–f), there were no significant differences both groups.

Figure 4: Preferred position for communication, situation a)–f), both groups

For exit warnings in situation a), both groups clearly marked with a bias to the approaching vehicle’s side (see Figure 5). Both groups focused on a taillight application, but also used projections next to the vehicle and the rear window. Especially the group without prior knowledge highlighted the opening door’s edge (max. 37 %). The results of both groups clearly show, that side-related information is needed for single-sided hazards, e.g. approaching vehicles when exiting the car.

Figure 5: Preferred position for communication, situation a) (exit warning), light department (A) and others (B)

In situation b)–d), we introduced hazardous situations in various distances (situation b): 50-100 m, situation c): 30-70 m, situation d): < 30 m, e.g. traffic jam end point, objects on road, emergency braking. For these warnings, participants concurred in marking taillights and rear windows as well as projections behind the vehicle (max. 18 %). Figure 6 also shows, that for the above mentioned situations combined, taillights (max. 75 %) are more important than the rear window (max. 63 %).

Figure 6: Preferred position for communication, situation b)–d) (hazardous situation on highway), light department (A) and others (B)

Nevertheless, taillights and rear windows are both important when it comes to a distance dependent communication in the vehicle’s rear. Figure 7 shows, that even though taillights are more important for all distances, their max. value of preferred

communication decreases with increasing distances. This is due to the fact that the rear window covers a larger area of the vehicle and therefore it is better recognizable over large distances. In contrast, when getting closer to the vehicle, e.g. < 30 m, almost 85 % of the participants see taillights as the optimal position for communicating a hazard warning.

Figure 7: Distance dependent position for communication, situation b)–d)

In situation e), distance violation, light department participants marked the rear window (max. 58 %), taillights (max. 47 %), and projections behind the vehicle (max. 42 %), while participants from other departments concentrated on the central brand logo (max. 42 %) and did not concur on other positions much. Relying more on large scale communication technologies shows, that a proximity warning takes advantage of an increasing apparent surface when warning others.

In situation f), autonomous parking, both groups marked the outer edges of taillights (max. 58 %) as well as of daytime running lights (max. 37 %). The light department additionally positioned a communication in projections around the vehicle (max 32 %), while other participants also used both wing mirrors (42 %). This clearly shows, that other road users want the autonomous parking mode being visible all around the vehicle and therefore, placing marker lamps on the outer edges of the lamps is advantageous.

4 Hardware Integration of communication functions: exterior display technologies

AUDI already introduced with “proximity indication” into rear combination lamps (RCLs) using digital OLED technology, the first light-based car-2-x communication function. The feature is adding a visual surface increase of the taillight signature at close distance situations – correlated to situation e) of the previous chapter. The function was introduced with the AUDI Q5 in 2020 and is meanwhile used in following product launches, including the 2021 AUDI A8 as series equipment.

In these lamps, segmented OLED lighting panels are used to create the taillight signature and to show the “proximity indication” function within a single component. Hence, a seamless integration into the RCL can be established and no extra elements for car-2-x communication have to be included. Thus, constructed space and costs are reduced in contrast to solutions that rely on extra hardware for solely doing communication.

In the future, next generation digital OLED will offer more segmentation with higher resolution [6]. This will enable new communication functions, including the use of symbols, benefiting from high precision and contrast of OLEDs enabling novel and extended communication features, e.g. as shown by the warning symbol in Figure 8.

Figure 8: RCL with Digital OLED Panels for seamless integration of communication (left image) and styling (right image) in one component

Adding more versatile digital OLED panels into the RCL is in accordance with the study results of Chapter 3. These show the highest score for an integration of warning functions into the RCLs. Especially, the taillight integration was favored by the survey participants for close distance situations up to 30 m. This can be used to enhance future safety features.

Next to OLED-based systems, also an-organic LED solutions, like LED-arrays or mini-LED (mLED) displays could be used for communication. However, these need a high

resolution if premium perception of taillight signatures is desired. An extensive comparison of exterior display technologies is given in [6] and shows these interdependencies. In addition, further pros and cons of OLED, AMOLED, mini-LED and micro-LED technologies for exterior display usage are discussed.

The study from Chapter 3 further indicates that several use cases demand an outboard position of an exterior display for optimum perception. This is challenging for most display technologies using rigid substrates as the outboard mounting position is in the car's wrap-around region with a pronounced curvature (curve radii $<250\text{mm}$). Hence, bendable substrate technologies would be beneficial allowing a seamless integration. At the moment, mLED displays are built with multi-layer PCBs with a high layer count, limiting it to 2D form-factors.

In contrast, bendable OLED technology could be a proper solution to smoothly integrate the OLED panel into this region, enabling car-2-x communication also on the side of the car, e.g. for extended communication especially in crossing- or turn-situations with pedestrians or cyclists. Especially, the high angular-stability of OLEDs' optical parameters, like high contrast, luminous intensity and homogeneity can enhance this application – outperforming LED-based approaches.

For higher luminance applications, predominantly in the front of the car, mLED-based approaches seem to be a promising option for the future but are not yet available.

The survey also points at, that for large distance communication with symbols, structure sizes are needed extending the dimensions of RCLs. Hence, other constructed space and technological solutions might boost the visibility distance of exterior communication, in the future, but are not yet available and have to be developed.

5 Summary and Outlook

Communication using exterior displays can be used for creating advantages for safety. Conducting a study on the optimal position of upcoming communication features for safety applications we found that over all situations, the participants focused for external communication mostly on taillights (max. 47 %) and rear windows (max. 42 %). For exit warnings, side-related information is needed for single-sided hazards, e.g. approaching vehicles when exiting the car. Regarding hazard warnings, e.g. traffic jam end point, objects on road, emergency breaking, participants focused on the vehicle's rear, while taillights (max. 75%) and rear window (max. 63%) were the most important positions.

The closer participants get to preceding vehicles, the more important are taillights for communication of warning signals. For distance violation we found that large scale communication technologies are needed, which means that a proximity warning takes advantage of an increasing apparent surface when warning others. The results for autonomous parking clearly show, that other road users want the autonomous parking mode being visible all around the vehicle and therefore, placing marker lamps on the outer edges of the lamps is advantageous.

We address the findings above with our OLED RCL, while no extra elements for car-2-x communication have to be included. Next generation digital OLED will offer more segmentation with higher resolution while HD resolution is only needed at low observation distances (\rightarrow RCL) [7].

The need for an outboard position of an exterior display for optimum perception can be addressed with bendable OLED technology. Other technological solutions might further boost the visibility distance of exterior communication, in the future, but are not yet available and have to be developed.

Acknowledgement

The authors would like to thank all partners within the Hi-Drive project for their cooperation and valuable contribution. [This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101006664. The sole responsibility of this publication lies with the authors. Neither the European Commission nor CINEA - in its capacity of Granting Authority.

6 References

- [1] B. Willeke, C. Hohmann, D. Mundt, A. Köhler, and A. Thoma, "HD Technologies: New Functions and Possibilities for Signal Lighting," in Darmstädter Lichttechnik, Proceedings of the 12th International Symposium on Automotive Lighting: ISAL 2017, T. Q. Khanh, Ed., München: utzverlag, 2017, pp. 349–356.
- [2] K. Merten, Informelle Zeichengebung im Straßenverkehr: Bericht zum Forschungsprojekt 7521 der Bundesanstalt für Straßenwesen Bereich

Unfallforschung. Köln: Bundesanstalt für Straßenwesen Bereich Unfallforschung, 1981.

[3] Q. Liu et al., “Rightward attentional bias in windshield displays: Implication Towards External Human Machine Interfaces for Self-driving Cars,” in 2017 IEEE Conference on Cognitive and Computational Aspects of Situation Management(CogSIMA), March 27-31, 2017 in Savannah, GA, USA.

[4] J. Kraft, “Entwicklung und Untersuchung der Kommunikation von Gefahrensymbolen über eine OLED-Rückleuchte im Automobilbereich,” Master Thesis, Produktentwicklung und Konstruktion, Otto von Guericke Universität Magdeburg, Magdeburg, 2022.

[5] AUDI AG, Exit warning. [Online] Available: <https://www.audi-mediacenter.com/en/photos/detail/exit-warning-42104>. Accessed on: Mar. 17 2023.

[6] M. Kruppa, W. Thomas, and J. Reschke, “Car2X Communication by Embedded Displays: Digital OLED Evolution Part 2,” in Darmstädter Lichttechnik, vol. 19, Proceedings of the 14th International Symposium on Automotive Lighting: ISAL 2021, T. Q. Khanh, Ed., München: utzverlag, 2022, pp. 443–453.

[7] J. Petit, E. Moisy, Lamberterie, and Antoine, “Style and signalling: display sizing for an optimized perception,” in Darmstädter Lichttechnik, vol. 19, Proceedings of the 14th International Symposium on Automotive Lighting: ISAL 2021, T. Q. Khanh, Ed., München: utzverlag, 2022, pp. 490–499.